

Self-development and personal growth how to improve your skills and achieve success in life

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Annotation: This article talks about self-development, personal growth, the place of reading in a person's life, secrets of skill development, methods of being successful, the role of mutoaladan in the formation of leader's speech. The role of mutoala in human life is of particular importance. Especially in the maturation of the leader, the role of books in his oratory development is incomparable. Each of us, whichever profession we are, will interact with the book to a certain extent, depending on our capabilities and circumstances. This is how we spend a certain part of our measured life

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A person must necessarily read the book in order to develop himself. The role of read in human life is of particular importance. Especially in the maturation of the leader, the role of books in his oratory development is incomparable. Each of us, whichever profession we are, will interact with the book to a certain extent, depending on our capabilities and circumstances. We spend a certain part of our measured life on it. But what kind of reading a book, its effects and consequences, in general, why we read a book, we will not all think about it in depth. Many people cannot read books, and many people do not understand more correctly why they are reading. Some see it as a difficult but only way to be educated. For them, any book will make a person "educated". And for others, reading is a pastime, just spending time and reading to them whatever, if not boring.

Just wanting to relax, spend time and grieving only about being "educated", the reader notices some unknown power in the book that purifies the heart, inspires the person. However, he cannot accurately imagine and evaluate this power. Such a reader looks like a patient who is completely unaware of medicine, that is, without understanding exactly what medicine is needed, begins to taste from each box. In fact, not every person should be able to find books that are

necessary for him, which give him new strength and spiritual influence, even when it comes to reading?

There is no point in knowing the history of world literature if not every read book brings joy and trouble, enthusiasm and spiritual freshness. Reading without reflection-khushmanzara means walking blindfolded in nature. We need to read not to forget ourselves and our life, but to realize the reins of life in a more conscious way. The book is required not to look like a cowardly student who looks at a dim-witted teacher, but to approach the conquest of the highest peak as an ardent climber. People spend a lot of time developing and educating themselves, but often new knowledge disappears in a black hole and does not help in any way in life. As a result, a week later, we will not be able to repeat the main ideas of the book we read. Or even worse - we left the courses after watching several lectures.

In order for self-education to be really effective, it must be treated as a business project. The development of personality begins in the early stages of a person's life. Childhood is the main stage in Personality Development. During this period, the child interacts with the environment, gaining experience and the main personal characteristics begin to form. Environmental factors such as family, education, friends, cultural values and experiences affect the development of the individual. In addition, genetic inheritance also forms the main building blocks of personal characteristics. The development of personality lasts from childhood to adolescence and puberty.

Self-development is a complex process that is final in the stages of personality creation. Sooner or later, a person comes to this mainly due to dissatisfaction, the desire to recognize himself as a person and the example of the surrounding society. A weak person is overwhelmed by fear, so he is not against him, but obeys the mentality of a herd. But opposing does not mean wrong. Rather, it means being individual, self-development and improvement. To achieve this, you need to constantly work on yourself, because self-development is not a privilege. Suppose you cannot spend all your research on one area of life, you get a job and only do it from morning to evening to make money. You need to start changing a little in each area of life, in small stages, so that you can achieve results. Self-development is a path that must go through certain stages of development. To begin with, get to know yourself, set the priorities of your life and ask yourself who you are in this world. Then you need to set goals, where you need to act, what result you want to achieve. They should be short-lived, not only for the long future, but also for lasting results, then the

incentive to act will be stronger. The next step will be a schedule of plans to achieve the desired result with small efforts and go step by step to your dream, achieve, achieve results, improve. After all, after taking a step, you can accumulate willpower and not relax on the road. The results can be surprising, they do not in vain say that a person is capable of even more than he thinks.

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